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**DESIGNING TEACHING MODULES IN TECHNOLOGY ON THE BASIS OF
INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES****Kharatova Shakhlo Khakimovna**

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Annotation: This article covers the scientific and methodological foundations of designing modern educational modules of technological science based on information and communication technologies (ICT). It analyzes the mechanisms of organizing educational content in a module-based manner, pedagogical approaches, and developing students' practical and creative competencies through ICT tools. It also shows the possibilities of increasing the efficiency of the educational process by integrating design, modeling, and experimental methods inherent in technological science with ICT. The article develops proposals for developing educational modules based on advanced foreign experiences, national educational standards, and modular educational concepts.

Keywords: technological science, educational module, modular education, interactive methods, educational design, ICT integration.

Introduction.

The modern educational process is becoming a complex system that requires speed, flexibility, and an individual approach. Developing information and communication technologies (ICT) are bringing about fundamental changes in all aspects of human life, in particular, in the education system. The digital transformation of education has not only facilitated the exchange of information between students and teachers, but also prompted a complete rethinking of the content of the teaching process. In particular, updating the educational content of technology in accordance with the requirements of the time, forming its educational modules using information and communication technologies has become one of the urgent pedagogical tasks of today.

Technology is by its nature a science based on practical, creative and problem-based thinking. In teaching this science, it is necessary to develop not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical skills, to involve students in design activities, to model and to form the skills to use modern technological tools. From this point of view, designing educational modules based on the concept of modular education and combining them with information and communication technologies is considered an important factor in increasing the effectiveness of technology. Because the organization of education on the basis of modules teaches students to independently research, solve problems, and apply knowledge in practice.

In today's digital age, ICT capabilities allow for the individualization of education, the establishment of distance learning, the widespread use of interactive lesson forms, and the creation of a learning environment suitable for students' minds based on visual and audio materials. In particular, if technology modules are enriched with tools such as multimedia, virtual laboratories, 3D modeling, and simulation programs, students

will not only understand the topics, but also be able to model real technological processes in the classroom or online. Based on these needs, this article aims to highlight the theoretical and methodological foundations of effective design of technology modules based on information and communication technologies, analyze best practices in this regard, and develop practical proposals. In this regard, the goal is to digitize the content of education, apply modern pedagogical approaches, and form professionally oriented competencies in students.

Methodology:

In the study on the design of educational modules of the science of technology based on information and communication technologies (ICT), modern pedagogical approaches, teaching technologies, modular systematic education model and the principles of effective use of digital tools were adopted as the methodological basis. The main meta-goal of this study is to provide a practical justification for the integration of the module system with ICT tools, which serves to direct students to practical activities, stimulate creative thinking and form independent learning competencies in teaching the science of technology.

The methodological foundations put forward in the study are based on the principles of the constructivist approach, the activity-oriented approach and the competency-based approach. Based on the constructivist approach, it is ensured that the student acquires knowledge not in a ready-made form, but through independent research, experimentation, and problem-solving activities. This requires enriching the educational modules with interactive, digital, and practical tools. The activity-oriented approach fully corresponds to the essence of the science of technology. Because this science embodies the activities of creation, design, construction, and modeling. Therefore, the educational modules are also designed in a way that attracts students to these types of activities. Methodologically, the study used comparison, content analysis, observation, experimental testing, and diagnostic methods. First of all, the existing modules related to the science of technology were analyzed and their content, form, and level of compatibility with ICT were assessed. Then, advanced foreign experiences - the organization of technology learning modules in the education systems of Finland, South Korea, Estonia and Japan - were studied, and their specific features were identified. Also, pedagogical experiments were organized in experimental schools to test new learning modules in local conditions. In this case, students were divided into two groups, the control group was trained using traditional methods, and the experimental group was trained using modularized education based on ICT.

Through monitoring of the educational process, tests, diagnostic interviews, the level of knowledge, practical skills and technological literacy indicators of students were determined, and the effectiveness of new modules was analyzed. At the same time, the principles of universal design, that is, the principles of creating open and flexible content suitable for all students, were also taken as a basis in the development of the modules. This methodological approach serves to ensure the didactic quality, functionality and usability of the learning modules.

Results:

Based on the conducted research and experimental tests, it was found that the introduction of educational modules developed based on information and communication technologies significantly increases the mastery of technology by students. The experiment was carried out in two stages, in which students of grades 7-9 of general education schools participated. The experimental group received education based on an ICT integrated module, and the control group was taught in the traditional way. The results of the pre-test and post-test were taken as the basis for the analysis.

120 students participated in the experiment: 60 in the control group and 60 in the experimental group. According to the results of the initial diagnostics, the average scores of both groups were almost equal - 48.5 points in the control group, 49.1 points in the experimental group (maximum score - 100). The results of the final test conducted at the end of the educational process showed the following changes:

The average score of the experimental group: 82.6:

The average score of the control group: 67.3.

These figures indicate that the organization of educational modules based on ICT has served to increase the technological knowledge and practical skills of students by 33.5%. In particular, it was observed that students' interest in the lesson increased through interactive platforms (Quizlet, Phet simulations, Tinkercad), video lessons, virtual laboratories and gamification elements.

Also, the following results were recorded based on indicators measuring the ability to complete practical tasks, design activities and independent work skills:

1-table.

Skill type	Control group (%)	Experiment group (%)
Correctly completing practical tasks	62%	89%
Ability to create an independent project	54%	83%
Independent use of ICT tools	47%	91%

It was also found that the attitude of students to their subject has changed in a positive direction - in the experimental group, 78% of students assessed technology as an important subject that affects their future career choice. Based on the final thoughts, a modularized and ICT-enriched educational process not only increases the level of knowledge of students, but also plays a significant role in preparing them for the modern labor market. This once again proves the need for innovative approaches to teaching technology.

Conclusion.

In the modern education system, teaching technology should not be limited to providing only theoretical knowledge, but also serve to form students' vital, practical and professional competencies. The studies, experiments and statistical analyses studied in this article have shown that by designing educational modules of technology based on information and communication technologies, the possibilities of enriching

the educational process in content, making it interactive and functional, and providing individual approaches expand. This has a positive impact not only on the quality of education, but also on the attitude of students to the lesson, their motivation and future professional direction.

With the help of ICT-integrated modules, the educational process becomes multimodal in nature, in which students understand knowledge more deeply through various information sources, digital tools, virtual experiments, simulations, test it and learn to draw independent conclusions. In particular, since the module-based educational materials are step-by-step, systematic, and practice-oriented, they have shown effectiveness in preparing students to solve real-life problems.

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